

Prove of Fermat's Last Theorem:

case of

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

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I proved that if $n \nmid XY$, only the form of ordered pair

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

can satisfy the Fermat equation.

But my previous proof is relying on other people's theorem.

So I decided to prove my own proof by ordered pair form above is impossible.

Lemma1.

If $\gcd(A, B) = 1$, and if the following equation holds true,

$$Aa = Bb$$

(all variables are natural numbers)

then the following must hold true:

$$1. A = bk$$

$$2. B = ak$$

pf) since A and B are coprime each other,

If we divide both sides by A ,

$$a = \frac{Bb}{A}$$

B cannot divide any prime factors of A .

Since a is a natural number, all prime factors of A in the denominator must be reduced.

Therefore b must be a multiple of A .

$$b = Ak_1$$

By similar logic, in

$$b = \frac{Aa}{B}$$

a is a multiple of B . $a = Bk_2$

$$Aa = Bb$$

We derived that

$$b = Ak_1, a = Bk_2$$

Substitute this into the equation.

$$A(Bk_2) = B(Ak_1)$$

$$\therefore k_2 = k_1$$

Let $k_1 = k_2 = k$.

$$k = \frac{b}{A} = \frac{a}{B}$$

$$\therefore aA = bB$$

[Definition]

Let

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_n(Z, X) \\ &= Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + Z^{n-3}X^2 + \dots + Z^2X^{n-3} + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

Then in the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$,

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

pf)

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

$$(Z - R^n)^n + (RA)^n = Z^n$$

$$R^n A^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Since $(Z - X) = R^n$,

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

In

$$\Phi_n(Z, X) = Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1} \quad (\alpha)$$

$$X = Z - R^n$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} X^{n-1} &= Z^{n-1} - \binom{n-1}{1} Z^{n-2} R^n + \dots - \binom{n-1}{n-2} Z (R^n)^{n-2} \\ &\quad + (R^n)^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$X^{n-1} = Z \times (\text{natural number}) + (R^n)^{n-1}$$

Substitute this into the equation (α)

Then

$$\Phi_n(Z, X) = Z \times (\text{natural number}) + (R^n)^{n-1}$$

$$\therefore \Phi_n(Z, X) \equiv (R^n)^{n-1} \pmod{Z}$$

Note that $A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X)$

$$A^n \equiv (R^{n-1})^n \pmod{Z}, (\because (R^n)^{n-1} = (R^{n-1})^n)$$

$$A^n - (R^{n-1})^n \equiv 0 \pmod{Z}$$

$$A^n - (R^{n-1})^n = (A - R^{n-1}) \times \Phi_n(A, R^{n-1})$$

This form is a multiple of Z . ($\gcd(A, R^{n-1}) = 1$)

I will show that $\Phi_n(A, R^{n-1})$ and Z are coprime.

Let's assume that

$$\gcd(\Phi_n(A, R^{n-1}), Z) = G \geq 2$$

Then $\Phi_n(A, R^{n-1})$ is a multiple of G .

$$\Phi_n(A, R^{n-1}) = \frac{A^n - (R^{n-1})^n}{A - R^{n-1}}$$

Since it is a multiple of G , we can let

$$\frac{A^n - (R^{n-1})^n}{A - R^{n-1}} = Gm$$

m is a suitable natural number.

$$A^n - (R^{n-1})^n = Gm(A - R^{n-1})$$

$$A^n - (R^{n-1})^n = GmA - GmR^{n-1}$$

$$A^n - GmA = (R^{n-1})^n - GmR^{n-1}$$

$$A(A^{n-1} - Gm) = R^{n-1}\{(R^{n-1})^{n-1} - Gm\}$$

Since $\gcd(A, R^{n-1}) = 1$, by Lemma1,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \{(R^{n-1})^{n-1} - Gm\}k \\ R^{n-1} &= \{A^{n-1} - Gm\}k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (R^{n-1})^{n-1}k - Gmk \\ R^{n-1} &= A^{n-1}k - Gmk \end{aligned}$$

Subtract the first equation from the second equation.

$$R^{n-1} - A = k \times \{A^{n-1} - (R^{n-1})^{n-1}\}$$

Since n is a prime number satisfies $n \geq 3$,

$\{A^{n-1} - (R^{n-1})^{n-1}\}$ has $\{A - R^{n-1}\}$ as a factor.

Then if we divide both sides by $\{A - R^{n-1}\}$,

$$-1 = k \times \{\text{cyclotomic polynomial}\}$$

Since A, R is natural numbers,

Each of the Cyclotomic polynomials of $\{A^{n-1} - (R^{n-1})^{n-1}\}$ is a natural number.

But $-1 = k \times \{\text{Cyclotomic polynomials}\}$

this doesn't make sense.

At least one cyclotomic polynomial cannot have the value 1 because it is connected only by addition.

So the initial assumption was wrong.

$\Phi_n(A, R^{n-1})$ and Z are coprime each other.

Therefore we get

$$Z \mid (A - R^{n-1})$$

But it is also contradiction. Because

$$X = Z - R^n > 0 \quad (\because X \text{ is a natural number})$$

$$Y = RA < Z$$

Therefore, $0 < A < Z$ and $0 < R^{n-1} < Z$

$$-Z < A - R^{n-1} < Z$$

it cannot be a multiple of Z .

Conclusion)

The following ordered pair form

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

cannot satisfy the Fermat equation.

In conjunction with the result of previous papers, Fermat's last theorem is true.

Thank you for reading.

Reference

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15252260>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15250439>